

Assessing Robot Navigation in Healthcare: A New Benchmarking Approach for Dynamic Environments

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Abstract—This work addresses the challenge of evaluating autonomous mobile robot navigation in hospitals by proposing a structured benchmarking protocol with quantitative performance metrics. Current navigation assessments in clinical environments suffer from a lack of standardization, limiting their use.

We introduce a series of progressively complex tests to assess robot performance. Applied to a realistic hospital scenario, the protocol was used to evaluate two autonomous mobile robots, HOSBOT and TIAGo, yielding reliable and reproducible results. These findings support the integration of robotics into healthcare by providing a robust framework for performance assessment.

Index Terms—Robot navigation, Hospital environment, Benchmarking method, SLAM, Healthcare mobile robots

I. INTRODUCTION

The adoption of robotics in healthcare has significantly increased in recent years, improving medical procedures and patient care by automating repetitive tasks, increasing efficiency, reducing costs and assisting clinical staff. Healthcare mobile robots are used for various functions, from drug and supply delivery to cleaning, disinfection, surgery and rehabilitation [1]. Evaluating their performance is crucial to ensure the safety of patients and healthcare workers, following standards, such as ISO 13482:2014 [2]. Hospitals represent complex and unstructured environments, with crowded spaces and obstacles, making robot navigation particularly challenging. Robot navigation systems use algorithms that combine data from sensors like LIDAR and cameras with localization and path-planning techniques. Performance metrics for navigation include safety aspects, path accuracy, and smoothness [3], but in hospital task success and safety are prioritized over other parameters and most existing studies focus on structured and static environments. The evaluation metrics in the presence of humans, such as path regularity and speed, have been mainly studied in pedestrian contexts [4], limiting their applicability to hospitals. Recent findings on disinfection and logistics

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robots during the Covid-19 pandemic often lacked real-world complexity, relying on laboratory tests with free navigation or at most static obstacles [5].

In summary, the literature highlights a lack of standardized protocols for the quantitative evaluation of autonomous robots in real hospital environments, and performance standards for deployment in such environments remain undefined. To fill this gap, we propose a quantitative method for evaluating the autonomous navigation capabilities of mobile robots in hospitals [6]. It includes a structured benchmarking protocol with standardized tests and comprehensive metrics that take into account the dynamic conditions of clinical environments.

II. THE PROPOSED APPROACH

The proposed approach consists of four batches of tests, increasing in complexity from free paths to those with static and dynamic obstacles. The tests include scenarios with no obstacles (NO), static obstacles (SO), moving obstacles (MO) and complex environments (CE), simulating realistic conditions, such as overcoming and passing obstacles. Each configuration includes three repetitions to assess the robots ability to operate safely, tested at three different velocities: $v_0 = 0.2m/s$, $v_1 = 0.6m/s$ and $v_2 = 1m/s$. Performance indicators include: i) Completion Time (CT): duration required to complete the task. It is defined as: $CT = t_f - t_0$ (where t_0 and t_f are the starting and ending time instants); ii) Path Length (PL): total distance to move from point A to point B and vice versa. It is

defined as: $PL = \frac{\int_{t_0}^{t_f} \dot{p}(t) dt}{d_{AB}}$ (where $\dot{p}(t)$ is the linear velocity of the robot and d_{AB} is the total distance traveled by the robot); iii) Distance Error (DE): error in reaching the desired position.

It is defined as: $DE = \frac{\|x_{goal} - x(t_f) - T_p\|}{T_p}$; iv) Orientation

Error (OE): error in reaching the desired orientation. It is defined as: $OE = \frac{\|o_{goal} - o(t_f) - T_o\|}{T_o}$ (where o_{goal} , $o(t_f)$ and T_o are respectively the desired and reached orientation in the reference frame and the tolerance in reaching goal orientation); v) Success Rate (SR): percentage of successfully completed navigation tasks. A test is considered failed in case of collision or if DE or OE are greater than their tolerances. It is defined

as: $SR = \frac{N_{succ}}{N_{tot}} 100$ (where N_{succ} and N_{tot} are respectively the number of accomplished and attempted assigned tasks); vi) Minimum Distance to Obstacles (MDO): minimum distance between the robot and nearby obstacles while navigating. It is defined as: $MDO = \min(D(t))$ (where $D(t)$ is the distance between robot and obstacle over time); vii) Time at Cruising Speed (TCS): percentage of time the robot travels at cruising speed with respect to the total time to perform the task. It is defined as: $TCS = \frac{T_{v_{set}}}{CT} 100$ (where $T_{v_{set}}$ is the time frame in which the robot moves at its cruising speed and the CT is previously defined). These indicators allow evaluating the efficiency, accuracy and safety of the robot during navigation. Statistical analysis is performed using the Wilcoxon test to compare the robots performance metrics at different speeds, with a significance level of $p = 0.05$, while Pearson's correlation assesses relationships and potential metric redundancies.

A. Experimental setup

The experimental tests, shown in Figure 1, was conducted in a simulated hospital environment replicating a real hospital layout (beds, corridors, waiting areas, and furniture) to ensure reliable robot testing without compromising patient safety.

The robots autonomous navigation performance was evaluated using the Vicon Vero optoelectronic system with 8 high-resolution cameras and reflective markers on the robotic platform and obstacles to track trajectories.

Two autonomous mobile robots (AMRs) were tested: HOSBOT, designed for hospital logistics, and TIAGo, conceived for human-robot interaction. HOSBOT consists of a commercial mobile base and a customized rack for transporting smart containers, while TIAGo has a 7-degrees-of-freedom arm, a gripper, RGB-D cameras and a speech synthesiser. Both robots use SLAM (Simultaneous Localisation and Mapping) algorithms to create maps of the environment and locate themselves in real time. The SLAM system comprises mapping and localisation, using sensors to detect obstacles and calculate position. The robots also use GMapping, which estimates the current position using a particle filter. This configuration allows testing and validation in unstructured scenarios.

Fig. 1. Experimental setup.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Results showed that both robots plan and execute a path even with obstacles, ensuring the target is reached within tolerance. However, this may not be sufficient for hospital applications, where avoiding collisions and ensuring adequate execution time for distances are crucial. As expected, CT decreases with increasing speed for both robots, with a significant reduction from v_0 (51.73 ± 0.81 s for HOSBOT and 48.10 ± 0.83 s for TIAGo) to v_1 (20.19 ± 0.16 s for HOSBOT and 22.50 ± 1.02 s for TIAGo). However, the OE increases with speed, with maximum values at v_2 . HOSBOT travelled approximately 10% more distance than TIAGo at v_1 and v_2 , reflecting structural differences. Both robots avoided collisions with static obstacles, demonstrating high reliability and SR . With moving obstacles, navigation becomes more complex, with longer CT and lower accuracy. For example, in complex environments, CT and PL increase, though SR remains high. The highest values of the correlation coefficients are obtained for the pairs $DE - OE$ and $CT - TCS$, 0.48 and 0.47 respectively. If a number of indicators are correlated, this suggests that they may capture similar aspects of performance, so that a set of them can be selected to prioritise or refine the measures to capture different aspects of performance and provide a more comprehensive assessment.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a structured method for benchmarking the autonomous navigation of mobile robots in a hospital environment through progressively more complex tests. Using an optoelectronic system, the navigation paths of two AMRs, HOSBOT and TIAGo, were evaluated and showed adequate performance in real-world scenarios. The results demonstrate the robustness and adaptability of the method, as well as its potential for setting minimum performance standards and developing guidelines for the safe and effective integration of autonomous robots in healthcare environments.

Future efforts will focus on collecting data from AMRs in hospitals using various navigation algorithms to assess their impact on performance and environmental requirements.

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